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Effect of Nitrogen on Seed Sugar Content in White Corn (*Zea Mays* L.)

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Abstract

A study conducted at Illinois State University research farms in 2021 and 2022 examined the effect of nitrogen (N) fertilizer on kernel sugar concentration, yield estimates, and grain mass in white corn (*Zea mays* L.). Using a randomized complete block design with two replications, nitrogen was applied as granular urea at rates of 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha. The grain yield was measured by hand-harvesting and shelling 1/1000th acre per plot and expressed as percent dry matter. Results showed no statistically significant differences between the replicates across the two seasons for sugar concentration, yield estimates, or grain yields. However, yield estimates increased linearly with higher nitrogen application rates, peaking at 150 kg N/ha. The average yield estimate was 12,552 kg/ha in 2021 and slightly higher at 12,687 kg/ha in 2022. Grain yield in 2022 exceeded that of 2021 by 844.1 kg. Nitrogen application also affected seed sugar content at all three milking stages. The findings suggest that nitrogen fertilization improves white corn yield and sugar concentration, but further research is needed to explore whether higher nitrogen levels maintain this linear trend. Additional studies should examine the moderating effects of weather conditions and soil moisture on nitrogen's impact on seed sugar content.

Keywords: Sugar concentration, White Corn, Brix %, Refractometer, Nitrogen, Yield estimate, Grain yield, Kernels, Fudge factor.

INTRODUCTION

White corn (*Zea mays* L.), also known as maize, is a globally cultivated grain crop characterized by kernels on a cob (Reddy et al., 2012). Believed to have originated in Mexico around 7000 years ago (Pruitt, 2016), evidence suggests its presence in the Southwestern United States as early as 2100 BC (Merrill et al., 2009). Two common varieties exist: field corn and sugary white corn. Field corn, harvested at late maturity, serves as livestock fodder and is processed into cereals, oil, and starch. Sugary corn, harvested immaturity at the 'milking' stage, is treated as a vegetable (Sinclair et al., 2020). The milking stage, approximately 20 days post-pollination, features kernels with a milky white fluid and high sugar and water content (Singh et al., 2014; Sinclair et al., 2020). This sweetness arises from a mutation in the *su* gene, which controls sugar-to-starch conversion (Singh et al., 2014). As the corn matures, kernels harden, with water and sugar content decreasing while starch content increases (Singh et al., 2014).

Kernel sugar concentration is typically measured using a refractometer, a rapid and inexpensive technique for assessing sugars and acids. The refractometer measures the bending of light through a liquid, with higher sugar

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content resulting in greater light bending and a higher Brix percentage. Brix represents the percentage by weight of sucrose in a pure water solution at 20°C. High-moisture, high-sugar white corn offers numerous benefits. It is consumed as a fresh or canned vegetable and used in processed foods and non-food products. White corn beverages serve as recovery drinks (Jusoh et al., 2019), while white corn residues replace wheat flour in baked goods (Lao et al., 2019). Corn sweeteners and high-fructose corn syrup are utilized in the sugar industry (Singh et al., 2014), and white corn stalks are used for bioenergy production (Pan-in & Sukasem, 2017) and animal feed (Zhou et al., 2019). White corn is a versatile food consumed in various forms worldwide (Malvar et al., 2008).

Corn production has increased since its domestication. Globally, maize production surpasses other major crops (Pruitt, 2016), with 1,137 million tons produced in TE2019, significantly more than rice and wheat (Erenstein et al., 2022). Global maize yields have nearly tripled in the last five decades (Erenstein et al., 2022). However, like other crops, corn production may be reaching a plateau (Ray et al., 2012). Immature white corn fetches higher prices but has relatively lower yields (Sinclair et al., 2020). Soil fertility, especially nitrogen (N), plays a crucial role in crop yield (Revilla et al., 2021). N fertilizer influences corn dry matter production, leaf area, photosynthetic capacity, and grain quality. Studies associate N application with improved crop quality and yields (Khan et al., 2017). However, limited research exists on the effect of Nitrogen on seed sugar content in white corn, with Sinclair et al. (2020) being a notable exception. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the effect of Nitrogen on seed sugar content in white corn, estimating kernel sugar concentration, establishing yield estimates and grain yield, investigating the response of white corn to Nitrogen fertilization, and documenting the effect of Nitrogen on seed sugar content in white corn. Independent sample t-tests and ANOVA tests were performed to determine whether any effects or interaction effects existed. Improving white corn quality is essential for meeting rising crop production demands. Understanding how to enhance white corn quality through appropriate methods would benefit farmers, policymakers, and overall economic development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Research Design

The experimental design was a 4 × 4 factorial arranged in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 2 replications; blocks 1&2 (as shown in figure 3.1 below) were used for replication. The two blocks were marked with pvc flags to distinguish the various plots on urea treatment. This also enabled the researcher to mark the various paths within the field during mowing. Nitrogen was applied as Granular Urea (46-0-0) at four rates (0, 50, 100, 150 kg N ha⁻¹) using broadcast method on each plot (See figure 1).

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Figure 3.1. The 4 × 4 factorial arranged plots in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 2 replications; blocks 1&2. The Key guides on the Nitrogen treatment at four rates (0, 50, 100, 150 Kg N/ha).

The Study Location

The study was conducted at the Illinois State University research farm in Lexington, IL 61753 (40.66844 N, 88.77591 W and 40.6710 N, 88.77178 W) in 2021 and 2022 respectively. General characteristics of the location included an average annual precipitation of 38.0 inches, with a rainy season from on March – July, hence sufficient to increase the soil moisture content and adequately support the growth of white corn seedlings without the need for additional measures such as irrigation. The predominant soil type was drummer silty clay loam (Fine-silty, mixed, superactive, mesic Typic Endoaquolls). Moreover, the land selected for this study had no prior manure history and in the previous years (2020 & 2021) was under soybean production. No soil testing was done prior to sowing to establish and document soil properties.

Figure 2. Illinois State University farm map

Cultural Practices in White Corn Production

The study was done over two years (2021 – 2022) with two cyclic planting and harvesting seasons (the planting & harvesting dates are summarized in table 1 below). Uniform white corn seeds (Pioneer Hybrid:

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P1120WYHR) were planted using traditional methods (fields were managed in no till – no till planter was mounted on a tractor), with a row spacing of 30-inches (2.5fts) and a planting depth of 1.5 cm. Nitrogen was applied as Granular Urea (46-0-0) at four rates (0, 50, 100, 150 kg N ha⁻¹) using a broadcast method on each plot. White corn seedlings were established, dependent solely on rainfall. The plots were kept weed free through regular weeding where overgrown weeds were pulled out and left on the plots as mulch.

Table I. Cultural practices dates for the 2 years at Illinois State University research farms in *Lexington (IL 61753)*

Cultural Practice	2021	2022
Site Coordinates	40.66844 N, 88.77591 W	40.6710 N, 88.77178 W
Planting dates	2 nd June 2021	16 th May 2022
Fertilizer Application dates	13 th June 2021	31 st May 2022
Mowing & regular weeding	2 nd July 2021 2 nd August 2021 2 nd September 2021	15 th June 2022 15 th July 2022 15 th August 2022
Corn sugar sampling	9 th – 15 th September 2021	10 th – 15 th July 2021
Harvesting dates	15 th October 2021	30 th September 2022

Corn Sugar Analysis

At the R3 (Milk) stage of corn growth (60th, 64th and 67th days upon emergence), 3 ears were the randomly handpicked on 1/1000th of an acre from each plot. To determine sugar concentration, a refractometer was utilized. A few drops of kernel juice were squeezed onto the refractometer's glass prism, closed the lid, and examined via the eyepiece. The corn sugar content was then read on a numbered scale in units called Brix (same as a percent).

Figure 3. An illustration on how to measure sugar concentration using a refractometer

White Corn Yield Estimate

The plant population was estimated at 35,000 plants/acre, determined by counting the plants in a row multiplied by four. The Yield estimates were determined by the Yield Component Method – developed by the Agricultural Engineering Department at the University of Illinois. The principal advantage to this method is that it can be used as early as the milk stage of kernel development. The yield component method involves use of a numerical

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constant for kernel weight that is figured into an equation to calculate grain yield. This numerical constant is sometimes referred to as a “fudge-factor” since it is based on a predetermined average kernel weight. To estimate grain yield, the Yield Component Method was used as follows:

- The number of harvestable ears in a length of row equivalent to 1/1000th acre was determined.
- On every fifth ear, the total number of kernel rows per ear and the average was determined. The sequence followed was that on every 5th, 9th, and 13th ears from one end of the row were picked.
- On each of these ears the total number of kernels per row and the average was determined.
- Yield (bushels per acre) is calculated by multiplying (ear number) by (average row number) and (average kernel number) and divide the results by 89.605*
- The procedure was repeated for each plot.

White Corn Grain Yield

At corn physiological maturity, 1/1000th acre per plot was hand-harvested and shelled. The percentage of dry matter was then determined as: $= (1 - \text{grain moisture } \%)$. To determine the pounds of dry matter per acre, we multiplied the grain weight \times percent dry matter \times 1000. Dry matter per acre was converted to 15.5% moisture ($1 - 0.155 = 0.845$) and a test weight of 56 pounds per bushel. The calculations were:

- Pounds of dry matter per acre \div 0.845 = Pounds of grain at 15.5% moisture
- Pounds of grain at 15.5% moisture \div 56 = Bushels of corn per acre at 15.5% moisture
- The Bu/A were then converted to KgHa-1.

Statistical Analysis

The independent variable was the Nitrogen treatment at different rates of application (0, 50, 100, & 150), whereas the study location and blocks were random factors. Dependent variables evaluated included the sugar concentration in white corn kernels, yield estimates of white corn, and white corn grain yield. Data was analyzed using the Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS V. 25) software. Both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis was performed. Descriptive analysis output was expressed as mean and standard deviation for the dependent variables across the 2 years (2021 & 2022). Inferential analyses entailed both independent sample t-tests and Analysis of Variance (One-way ANOVA) for mean comparisons. All statistical tests (T-test & ANOVA) were conducted at 95% C.I with the P-value for statistical significance set at $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Additionally, the t-value/t-statistic (for the student T-test) and the F-ratio & F-crit (for the ANOVA test) were evaluated rigorously to see whether the differences were statistically significant, thereby providing enough information to support the null hypotheses (whether to reject the null hypotheses or accept).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Environmental Conditions at Lexington IL, research farms

There was similarity on the trends of average monthly temperatures throughout the May-November season for 2021 and 2022 (Tables 2 and 3). As the season progressed, the average high and low temperatures rose during June, July, and August before beginning to decline in August. Notably, the year 2021 was relatively cold compared to 2022. The peak high average in 2022 was 3.69°F higher than that of 2021, while the peak low average was 2.59°F higher. Similarly, the rainfall patterns for both years showed similar trends, with the highest rainfall being recorded in June followed by October and August (Tables 2 and 3).

Similarly, the precipitation in 2022 was reduced compared with that of 2021. Rainfall in 2021 was greater than that of 2022 by 47.75mm. The lowest rainfall recorded reduced by 1.5 mm from that recorded in 2021. This is in line with Wuebbles et al. (2021), who reported that climate change has caused 1-2°F increases in average daily temperatures in Illinois in the past century and is projected to cause further temperature increases statewide. Additionally, extreme precipitation events observed during the study are also evidence of the

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changing weather conditions due to global warming.

Table 2. Environmental Conditions in 2021

Month	Temperature (°F) 2021		Rainfall 2021	
	<i>High Average</i>	<i>Low Average</i>	<i>Ppt (inches)</i>	<i>Ppt (mm)</i>
May	76.25	43.13	1.41	35.81
June	82.00	64.13	4.32	109.73
July	80.38	64.17	1.41	35.81
August	83.11	66.63	1.89	48.01
September	76.58	57.27	0.84	21.34
October	74.42	45.71	2.58	65.53
November	53.63	24.67	0.3	7.62

Table 3. Environmental Conditions in 2022

Month	Temperature (°F) 2022		Rainfall 2022	
	<i>High Average</i>	<i>Low Average</i>	<i>Ppt (inches)</i>	<i>Ppt (mm)</i>
May	81.19	48.87	0.87	22.10
June	86.08	63.33	2.44	61.98
July	85.79	69.22	0.71	18.03
August	80.00	65.56	0.77	19.56
September	78.29	50.12	0.24	6.10
October	61.80	39.00	0.72	18.29

Corn Yield Estimate and Grain Yields

There were no statistically significant differences between the mean samples from the two replicates (blocks 1 & 2) across the two seasons for corn yield estimates and grain yields. The yield estimates and grain yields were slightly higher in 2022 than in 2021 (Figure 4 & 5). In 2021, the mean yield estimate was 12,552 Kg ha⁻¹, while that of 2022 averaged 12687 Kg ha⁻¹. Similarly, the grain yield achieved in 2022 was 844.1kg more than the average grain yield in 2021.

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Figure 4. White corn mean yield estimate (Kg/Ha) with standard deviation error bars in 2021 & 2022

Figure 5. White corn mean grain yield (Kg/Ha) with standard deviation error bars in 2021&2022

The slight differences in mean yield estimate and grain yield between 2021 and 2022 were corroborated by other studies. For instance, Gheith et al. (2022) found that corn yield increased by 100 Kg ha⁻¹ in the second year of the nitrogen treatment. An earlier study (Ray et al., 2019) also recorded a 7% increase in yield in the second year of their nitrogen study. These slight improvements in yield can be attributed to varied nitrogen fertilization in the crops farmed in the previous years. Fertilizers applied in the plots in 2021 during soybean cultivation could have contained some residual nutrients that may have benefitted the crops in the following planting season.

Corn Sugar Characteristics

Similarly, there were no statistically significant differences between the mean samples of the corn sugar concentrations from the two replicates (blocks 1 & 2) across the two seasons. The corn sugar content was assessed at 3 corn growth (milking) stages (60th, 64th and 67th days upon emergence). Overall, the sugar

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content was higher in 2021 than 2022. On the 60th day, the average soluble sugar content in 2021 was 12.23 Brix% (Figure 6), which was 5% higher than that recorded in 2022 (Figure 4.4). On 64th day the sugar content in 2022 (Figure 7) was 9% lower than that of 2021 (Figure 4.3). The differences in sugar content of the corn seeds may have been caused by the weather changes observed during the study. The 2021 season received higher rainfall and lower temperatures than the 2022 season. Higher temperatures cause higher evaporation, leaving the soil drier (Tang et al., 2017). This effect is worsened when there is reduced precipitation, and without irrigation, the soil gets less moisture. As Wang et al. (2021) observed, soil moisture content affects the sugar content of crops, with crops getting the most moisture yielding more sugar in their harvested products. Therefore, the reduced soil moisture content could explain the reduced seed sugar content observed in the second year of our study.

Figure 6. White corn mean sugar concentration (Brix %) with standard deviation error bars at different growth stages in 2021

Figure 7. White corn mean sugar concentration (Brix %) with standard deviation error bars at different growth stages in 2022

Sugar concentration reduced with maturity, as the concentration was highest on the 60th day and lowest on the 67th day. The average soluble sugar content on the 60th day was 12.23 Brix% (± 1.26), which reduced to 11.26 Brix% (± 1.07) on the 64th day in 2021. In 2022, the content on day 60 was 11.59 Brix% (± 1.75), decreasing to 10.27 Brix% (± 1.67) on day 64 and 8.76 Brix% (± 1.74) on day 67. These results are in line with Yue et al. (2022), who reported that sucrose content increases with growth, up to a certain point where it then begins to drop. In their study, they found that sucrose content in corn seeds increases steadily after pollination, peaking at 14 days after pollination from where it starts to decrease as growth progresses. The opposite was observed for starch, which increased further after 14 days, to peak at 35 days post-pollination. This indicates that as the plant matures, sugar in the seeds is continuously converted to starch, to yield high starch contents and low sugar contents at maturity.

Corn Yield Characteristics under Different Nitrogen Application Levels

Yield characteristics showed a positive response to nitrogen application in both seasons, whereby, there was a linear increase in yield with an increase in nitrogen (Table 4). The highest yields were achieved when nitrogen

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fertilizer was applied at 150kg ha⁻¹, while the least was recorded without any nitrogen fertilization. In 2021, the application of nitrogen at 50kg ha⁻¹ increased the yield estimate by 5%, 100kg ha⁻¹ by 16%, and 150kg ha⁻¹ by 23% compared with the yield from unfertilized corn plants. The grain yield was 8% higher in crops planted with 50kg Nha⁻¹, 20% higher at 100kg Nha⁻¹, and 26% higher at 150kg Nha⁻¹ than the yield at 0kg Nha⁻¹ in 2021. Surprisingly, the same margins of differences in grain yield between the 0kg Nha⁻¹ treatment and 100kg Nha⁻¹ (20%) and 150kg Nha⁻¹ (26%) treatment groups were observed both in 2021 and 2022. Conversely, the yield estimates showed higher margins between the 0kg Nha⁻¹ treatment and other nitrogen treatments in 2022 than in 2021. In 2022, the yield under 150kg Nha⁻¹ was 30% higher than the unfertilized group, while 100kg Nha⁻¹ and 50kg Nha⁻¹ were 21% and 11% higher, respectively.

Table 4. Yield Characteristics at Different Nitrogen Application Levels

Variables	N treatment	Block 1		Block 2		Blocks 1 & 2			
		N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	N	Mean	Std. Dev
2021									
Yield estimate (Kg ha⁻¹)	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11240.94	537.99	11298.95	175.92	8	11269.95	371.84
	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12125.68	352.07	11755.52	552.48	8	11940.60	472.32
	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	13042.63	349.95	13104.82	307.95	8	13073.73	306.97
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	13798.99	194.55	14048.44	598.99	8	13923.71	433.32
Grain yield (Kg ha⁻¹)	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11954.99	1298.77	11746.42	1499.23	8	11850.70	1303.32
	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	13275.13	495.26	13017.86	240.61	8	13146.49	385.80
	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	14387.00	209.70	14354.28	689.77	8	14370.64	472.29
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	15382.80	1337.83	15512.51	410.81	8	15447.66	918.80
2022									
Yield estimate (Kg ha⁻¹)	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11039.92	363.47	11216.03	443.66	8	11127.98	387.09
	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12046.55	563.67	12151.63	322.36	8	12099.09	428.79
	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	13578.63	376.01	13258.81	594.04	8	13418.72	490.97
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	14167.06	680.23	14037.29	598.88	8	14102.17	597.35
Grain yield (Kg ha⁻¹)	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	13097.40	1512.23	12292.20	836.34	8	12694.80	1210.41
	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	14452.90	1580.30	13943.42	775.84	8	14198.16	1184.24
	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	15646.59	610.13	14911.90	1319.73	8	15279.25	1029.66
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	16512.64	2448.93	15526.74	2229.14	8	16019.69	2231.04

The mean differences in yield estimates between and within the four N treatment groups in 2021 were statistically significant at 95% C.I (table 5).

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Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test summary on Yield characteristics 2021

Variables	ANOVA		
	Blocks 1 & 2	Block 1	Block 2
Yield estimate (Kg/ha)	$F_{3, 28} = 69.159,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 34.362,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 32.072,$ $p < 0.001$
Grain yield (Kg/ha)	$F_{3, 28} = 26.46,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 9.233,$ $p = 0.002$	$F_{3, 12} = 14.441,$ $p < 0.001$

The Tukey post hoc test revealed that the mean yield estimates were significantly higher after treating white corn with 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (11940.60 ± 472.32 Kg/ha, $p = 0.012$), 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13073.73 ± 306.97 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$), & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13923.71 ± 433.32 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) compared to 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (11269.95 ± 371.84 Kg/ha). Additionally, treating with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13073.73 ± 306.97 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13923.71 ± 433.32 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) resulted in significantly higher mean yield estimates compared to 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (11940.60 ± 472.32 Kg/ha), whereas, treating the corn with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13923.71 ± 433.32 Kg/ha, $p = 0.001$) had a higher mean yield estimate compared with treating corn with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13073.73 ± 306.97 Kg/ha).

In the same year, there were statistically significant mean differences in the grain yield between and within the various N treatment groups at 95% C.I (Table 6). According to the Tukey Post Hoc test (annex 1a), the mean grain yield was significantly higher after treating white corn with 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (13146.49 ± 385.80 Kg/ha, $p = 0.025$), 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (14370.64 ± 472.29 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$), & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (15447.66 ± 918.80 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) compared to 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (11850.70 ± 1303.32 Kg/ha). Similarly, the corn treated with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (14370.64 ± 472.29 Kg/ha, $p = 0.037$) & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (15447.66 ± 918.80 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) had significantly higher mean grain yield compared to 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (13146.49 ± 385.80 Kg/ha). For the corn treated with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ and 150 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.078$), there were no statistically significant differences in the grain yield.

Similarly, in 2022, both the yield estimate and grain yield were all statistically significant at 95% C.I – between the N treatment groups as determined by one-way ANOVA tests shown in the ANOVA results summary table 6 below.

Table 6. 2022 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test summary on Yield characteristics

Variables	ANOVA		
	Blocks 1 & 2	Block 1	Block 2
Yield estimate (Kg/ha)	$F_{3, 28} = 60.849,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 30.903,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 24.229,$ $p < 0.001$
Grain mass (Kg/ha)	$F_{3, 28} = 7.495,$ $p = 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 3.158,$ $p = 0.064^*$	$F_{3, 12} = 3.973,$ $p = 0.035$

The Tukey Post Hoc test further revealed that the 2022 findings observed in the yield estimates were like those documented in the previous year. The mean yield estimates were significantly higher after treating white corn with 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (12099.09 ± 428.79 Kg/ha, $p = 0.002$), 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13418.72 ± 490.97 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$), & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (14102.17 ± 597.35 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) compared to 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (11127.98 ± 387.09 Kg/ha). Additionally, treating with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13418.72 ± 490.97 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (14102.17 ± 597.35 Kg/ha, $p < 0.001$) resulted in significantly higher mean yield estimates compared to 50 kg Nha⁻¹

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(12099.09 ± 428.79 Kg/ha), whereas, treating the corn with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (14102.17 ± 597.35 Kg/ha, p = 0.04) had a higher mean yield estimate compared to treating corn with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (13418.72 ± 490.97 Kg/ha).

The mean differences in the grain yield were only significant between the two N treatment groups: 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ and 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹. The mean grain yield was significantly higher in the 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (16019.69 ± 2231.04 Kg/ha, p = 0.001) treatment group and 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (15279.25 ± 1029.66 Kg/ha, p = 0.009) treatment group compared to 0 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment group (12694.80 ± 1210.41 Kg/ha). The mean differences in grain yield observed in the remaining groups were not statistically significant. These groups include: 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.207), 50 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.481), 50 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.092), and 100 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.755).

As nitrogen is an important nutrient for all plants, increased nitrogen application is expected to produce higher yields. This is evident in our study, as in other studies that have previously shown this effect in corn, with some reporting higher effects than others (Gheith et al., 2022; Yue et al., 2022; Ray et al., 2019). Yue et al. (2022) reported an annual yield increase of over 200% in the corn treated with 300kg Nha⁻¹ and an 185% increase in under 200kg Nha⁻¹ compared with unfertilized corn. However, their study evaluated the effect of both nitrogen level and application time. In that case, both factors were shown to interact and cause these high effects. As similar to our study, Ray et al. (2019), recorded higher margins of yield, and observed that increasing nitrogen fertilizer application from 100kg ha⁻¹ to 200kg ha⁻¹ increased yield by 12% while increasing to 250kg ha⁻¹ yielded a 20% yield increase.

In contrast, Omar et al. (2022) used application levels (0, 50, 100, and 150kg Nha⁻¹) as in our study but did not find a corresponding linear increase in yield. The researchers found that the highest yield was achieved at 50kg Nha⁻¹, with additional increases causing a reduction in yield. Omar and colleagues applied the nitrogen fertilizer once at the vegetative stage (V12). Conversely, other studies used more than one application times done before the V12 stage (Gheith et al., 2022; Yue et al., 2022; Ray et al., 2019). The differences in application times could explain the variation in results observed.

Sugar Characteristics under Different Nitrogen Application Levels

The effect of nitrogen application level on seed sugar content was evident at all three milking stages. The application of nitrogen caused a linear increase in seed sugar content (Table 7). The highest sugar content in 2021 was 13.75 Brix%, which was recorded on 60th day in plants under fertilization of 150kg Nha⁻¹ fertilization. The 150kg Nha⁻¹ treatment group also recorded the highest sugar content of 13.56 Brix% on 60th day in 2022. Sugar content tested on 60th day showed that the addition of nitrogen fertilizer at 50kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a 5% increase, while 100kg ha⁻¹ and 150kg ha⁻¹ increased yield by 8% and 24%, respectively in 2021. In the same year, sugar content on 64th day was increased by 14% under 100kg Nha⁻¹ and 19% under 150kg Nha⁻¹, compared with 0kg Nha⁻¹.

Interestingly, the addition of 50kg ha⁻¹ N caused a slight reduction of 2% on 60th day, 4% on 64th day, and 1% on 67th day in the corn sugar content in 2022. Nevertheless, the addition of nitrogen to 100kg ha⁻¹ and 150kg ha⁻¹ resulted in increased sugar content at all three stages. The 100kg Nha⁻¹ treatment group had 13% higher seed sugar content than the 0kg Nha⁻¹ group on 60th day, while the sugar content on 64th day was 7% higher and that on 67th day was 21% higher. Despite the values for sugar content being lower in 2022 than in 2021, higher margins of increase were observed under 150kg Nha⁻¹ in 2022 than in 2021. The seed sugar content under 150kg Nha⁻¹ was 28% higher than the control group (0kg Nha⁻¹) on 60th day and 27% higher on 64th day in 2022. These values were 4% and 8% higher than the 2021 values on 60th day and 64th day, respectively.

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Table 7. Corn Sugar Concentration at Different Nitrogen Levels

Variables	N treatment	Block 1			Block 2		Blocks 1 & 2		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	N	Mean	Std. Dev
2021									
Brix % on	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11.06	0.31	11.00	0.20	8	11.03	0.25
60th day	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11.63	1.09	11.56	1.51	8	11.59	1.22
(8/25/2021)	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12.94	0.59	12.13	0.25	8	12.53	0.60
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	14.19	0.43	13.31	0.24	8	13.75	0.57
Brix % on	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.38	0.48	10.31	0.77	8	10.34	0.60
64th day	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.50	0.89	10.44	0.66	8	10.47	0.73
(8/30/2021)	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12.00	0.82	11.75	0.20	8	11.88	0.57
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12.63	0.75	12.06	0.52	8	12.34	0.67
2022									
Brix % on	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	11.11	0.63	10.00	1.41	8	10.56	1.18
60th day	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.38	1.70	10.25	1.26	8	10.31	1.39
(8/12/2022)	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12.38	1.09	11.50	1.00	8	11.94	1.08
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	14.00	1.35	13.13	1.03	8	13.56	1.21
Brix % on	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.19	0.38	8.88	1.93	8	9.53	1.47
64th day	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	9.13	2.02	9.19	1.01	8	9.16	1.48
(8/15/2022)	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.88	0.85	9.69	0.94	8	10.28	1.05
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	12.56	0.83	11.69	0.94	8	12.13	0.94
Brix % on	0 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	8.38	0.48	7.00	1.96	8	7.69	1.51
67th day	50 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	7.69	2.10	7.50	1.29	8	7.59	1.61
(8/19/2022)	100 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	9.88	0.85	8.75	1.04	8	9.31	1.07
	150 kg Nha ⁻¹	4	10.88	0.72	10.00	1.15	8	10.44	1.01

The application of nitrogen fertilizer caused a statistically significant linear increase in the seed sugar content of corn grain at the three milking stages. One-way ANOVA tests performed, showed that there were statistically significant mean differences (95% C.I) in the corn sugar content on all the three milking stages (60th, 64th & 67th day) between and within the 4 N treatment groups (0, 50, 100, 150 kg N/ha) in both 2021 & 2022 as shown in table 8 below.

Table 8. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) tests summary on the corn sugar concentration in 2021 & 2022

Years	Variables	ANOVA		
		Blocks 1 & 2	Block 1	Block 2
2021	Brix % on 60 th day (8/25/2021)	$F_{3, 28} = 20.306,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 17.201,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 6.438,$ $p = 0.008$
	Brix % on 64 th day (8/30/2021)	$F_{3, 28} = 19.531,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 8.815,$ $p = 0.002$	$F_{3, 12} = 9.568,$ $p = 0.002$
2022	Brix % on 60 th day (8/12/2022)	$F_{3, 28} = 12.089,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 6.386,$ $p = 0.008$	$F_{3, 12} = 5.797,$ $p = 0.011$
	Brix % on 64 th day (8/15/2022)	$F_{3, 28} = 8.825,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 5.929,$ $p = 0.01$	$F_{3, 12} = 3.916,$ $p = 0.037$
	Brix % on 67 th day (8/19/2022)	$F_{3, 28} = 8.531,$ $p < 0.001$	$F_{3, 12} = 5.66,$ $p = 0.012$	$F_{3, 12} = 3.653,$ $p = 0.044$

The ANOVA tests were followed up with Tukey post-hoc tests/multiple comparison tests to understand the differences between & within the treatment groups. In 2021, Brix % on 60th day was statistically significantly higher after treating the white corn with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (12.53 ± 0.60 Brix%, $p = 0.002$) and 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13.75 ± 0.57 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) compared with 0 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (11.03 ± 0.25 Brix%). Additionally, treating the corn with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13.75 ± 0.57 Brix%) resulted in statistically significant higher Brix % on 60th day compared to treating with either 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (11.59 ± 1.22 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) or 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (12.53 ± 0.60 Brix%, $p = 0.014$). There were no statistically significant differences between treatment with 0 kg Nha⁻¹ and 50 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.447$) and between 50 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment and 100 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment ($p = 0.08$).

On 64th day (8/30/2021), the Tukey post hoc tests revealed similar findings (Annex 1a). The mean Brix % was statistically significantly higher after treating white corn with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (11.88 ± 0.57 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) and 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (12.34 ± 0.67 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) compared with 0 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (10.34 ± 0.60 Brix%). Additionally, there were statistically significant differences in the mean Brix% between 50 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (10.47 ± 0.73 Brix %) & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (11.88 ± 0.57 Brix%, $p = 0.001$), and 50 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (10.47 ± 0.73 Brix %) & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ treatment (12.34 ± 0.67 Brix%, $p < 0.001$). There were no statistically significant differences between treatment with 0 kg Nha⁻¹ and 50 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.98$) and between treatment with 100 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.474$).

In 2022, varied results were observed at the three milking stages. On the 60th day (8/12/2022), there were statistically significant mean Brix % differences only between white corn treated with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ & 0 kg Nha⁻¹, and 150 kg Nha⁻¹ & 50 kg Nha⁻¹. White corn treated with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (13.56 ± 1.21 Brix%) had a significantly higher Brix% when compared to corn treated with either 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (10.31 ± 1.39 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) or 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (10.56 ± 1.81 Brix%, $p < 0.001$). There was no statistically significant mean Brix% differences observed for corn treatment between the following groups: 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 50 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.978$), 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.129$), 50 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.57$), and 100 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ ($p = 0.057$).

On 64th day (8/15/2022), the only observed statistically significant mean Brix% differences were only between white corn treated with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ and any of the remaining 3 N treatment groups. Treating corn with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (12.13 ± 0.94 Brix%) resulted in significantly higher Brix% compared to treating with either 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (10.28 ± 1.05 Brix%, $p = 0.032$), 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (9.16 ± 1.48 Brix%, $p < 0.001$) or 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (9.53 ± 1.47 Brix%, $p < 0.002$). There was no statistically significant mean Brix% differences observed for corn treatment between

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the following groups: 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.932), 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.636), and 50 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.299).

On 67th day (8/19/2022), similar findings as those reported on 60th day (8/12/2022) were observed. White corn treated with 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (10.44 ± 1.01 Brix%) had a significantly higher Brix% compared to corn treated with either 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (7.59 ± 1.61 Brix%, p = 0.001) or 0 kg Nha⁻¹ (7.69 ± 1.51 Brix%, p < 0.002). There was no statistically significant mean Brix% differences observed for corn treatment between the following groups: 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 50 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.999), 0 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.091), 50 kg Nha⁻¹ & 100 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.068), and 100 kg Nha⁻¹ & 150 kg Nha⁻¹ (p = 0.345).

The study found that nitrogen fertilization increases the amounts of soluble sugar content in corn at the milking stage. As other studies have observed, enzymes involved in soluble sugar synthesis are heightened under nitrogen fertilization (Yue et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2019). The increased sucrose synthase and sucrose phosphate synthase activity observed at the grain-filling stage corresponds with the high sugar content found in corn grain at the milking stage (Yue et al., 2022). When the enzyme activity increases following the addition of nitrogen fertilizer, corresponding sugar content increases are recorded, as observed in our study. Like in our study, Wu et al. (2019) showed that increasing fertilizer application from 150kg ha⁻¹ to 450kg ha⁻¹ increased the soluble sugar content in the corn grain. As Yue et al. (2022) reported, sucrose accumulation regulates the starch content in corn grain. Increased accumulation of sucrose provides the necessary intermediaries for starch synthesis, leading to a reduction in sucrose content as more starch is synthesized. Consequently, the reduction in soluble sugar content recorded with the progression of growth towards maturity in our study results from the conversion of sugars into starch.

Our study also recorded the reduced effect of nitrogen fertilization on soluble sugar content as the plant neared maturity. In 2021, there was a 24% increase in sugar content on 60th day and a 19% increase on 64th day following fertilization at 150kg Nha⁻¹. The same was recorded in 2022, with a 28% increase being recorded on 60th day and a 27% increase on 64th day. Wu et al. (2019) also recorded consistent findings, reporting that the effect of nitrogen fertilization on sugar content in the grain was lower at R5 than at the R1 and R3 stages. Additionally, Yue et al. (2022) found that the starch synthase level increased with maturity and with the application of nitrogen fertilizer. This implies that nitrogen positively influences the amount of starch accumulating towards maturity, which negatively affects the soluble sugar level towards maturity. This could be the reason why the effect of nitrogen on soluble sugar content was lower on 64th day than on the 60th day of corn emergence.

The results of this study showed that nitrogen fertilization has a significant impact on the yield and sugar content of sweet corn. At 150 kg N ha⁻¹, the highest grain mass and sugar levels are produced, especially when the corn is harvested early (60 days post-emergence). Differences between 0 and 50 kg N ha⁻¹ were statistically insignificant, but the sugar content rose linearly with nitrogen up to 150 kg N ha⁻¹. The sugar content was further impacted by seasonal variations (2022 being warmer/wetter), indicating unmeasured soil moisture interactions. Among the recommendations are filling in the gaps in soil moisture dynamics, investigating nitrogen levels above 150 kg N ha⁻¹ to evaluate possible yield and sugar content plateaus or declines, and repeating the study in a variety of climatic conditions to confirm weather-related impacts.

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